

REVISITING THE CONCEPT OF INDONESIA'S MAIN ISLAND DEFENSE IN CRAFTING A RELEVANT ARCHIPELAGIC DEFENSE STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Geography and history are two factors determining a country's defense behavior. Indonesia is not an exception. It has a fragmented shape due to its geography as a vast archipelago. Its history of experiencing armed conflicts was a history of establishing and maintaining political unity over such a fragmented territory. In dealing with these two determinants, Indonesia has developed an archipelagic defense strategy with main island defense as its core. Under this defense system, every main island and major island chain should be able to defend itself independently during a military emergency. However, the authors argued that such a doctrine needs to be rethought to make it relevant in dealing with Indonesia's current threats, including the external threat of the South China Sea conflict and the internal threat of terrorism and separatism.

Keywords: main island defense; territorial commands; threats.

1. INTRODUCTION

To understand the national security of a country, especially a country's behavior in maintaining its existence, it is important to consider the geography (Drohan, 2018; Gray, 2016) and history of the nation-state in question (Laksmana, Gindarsah, & Maharani, 2020; Prabowo, 2012). In terms of geography, archipelagic countries have unique characteristics distinguishing them from the mainland and coastal countries, resulting in different behavior when securing their national interests. Archipelagic countries' territory is naturally 'fragmented'. Indonesia was an extreme example of a state with such a fragmented shape (Rubenstein, 2016). Its territory, consisting of tens of thousands of islands—including its five biggest islands—was dominated by waters. Among the large islands or groups of islands that make up the territory, many were even separated by waters that stretch more than 12 nautical miles, a distance that traditionally designates the limit of countries' territorial waters (Butcher & Elson, 2017; Djalal, 1990). Before the ratification of the UNCLOS of 1982 and the codification of the concept of an

‘archipelagic state’ (Draper, 2018) in the Law of the Sea, Indonesia cannot deny the fact that its shape remains fragmented regardless of its political integrity. It can be said, then, that in the context of developing defense behavior, geography, including the vast archipelago of Indonesia, serves as a determinant.

The second factor, history, is more dynamic than geography. In terms of national security, the primary narratives of a country’s history are mostly about the threats to its existence, and how it attempts to resolve such threats in its journey to establish itself as a solid political entity. All of these are bound to the geographical condition as an arena staging such historical events comes into play. Likewise, to understand Indonesia and the development of its military, it is necessary to consider what is perceived as a threat at a time. For a matter of clarity and simplicity, we can categorize such threats into domestic ones stemming from the internal dynamics of power relations between different social and/or political actors within its border, like separatism, domestic terrorism, and social unrest, and foreign ones emerging from the external geopolitical development, as like invasion or other form of conventional threats.

As such, it is obvious that Indonesia’s defense behavior was also determined by what it perceives as a threat and how it makes use of its archipelagic territory as a stage to orchestrate necessary measures against the emergent threat. Any explanation concerning strategy, tools, and resources that are useful for defending a country from the invasion of other parties, including military troops and weapons, is only meaningful when put against these two determinants: history (of war and political conflict) and geography. The explanation, on the one hand, must be able to consider how the existing resources are utilized to eliminate threats. On the other hand, such explanations must also consider how the defense resources, particularly troops and weapons, are distributed and should be mobilized across the real geographical arena to maintain the political integrity of the country occupying such specific geography. It means, in short, it is crucial to discuss how the military is spatially organized in the time of peace so it can be mobilized effectively in the time of war.

Against such a background, this article aims to discuss how Indonesia’s military organization is shaped to meet the needs of securing and maintaining its political integrity. It will depart from the territorial feature of the Indonesian Armed Forces, especially the Army, whose territorial commands were structured by mirroring the organization of civilian government, from sub-district commands (Komando Rayon Militer/Koramil) at the bottom of the structure up to regional commands (Komando Daerah Militer/Kodam) as the highest territorial organization.

In its development, this kind of organization has proven to be quite effective in defending Indonesia’s territorial integrity from hostile forces in the past. The *wehrkreise* or ‘military region’ system was effectively used by the Indonesian military during the war of independence (1945–1949) to stem the Dutch invasion. This system was later also developed and modified to localize rebellion in various regions during the parliamentary democracy (1950–1959). As the heir to the *wehrkreise* system, the territorial commands become an important instrument to foster security and defense in the region for decades to come, including for early detection and prevention of potential treasons or rebellions.

However, in the context of the contemporary strategic environment, the possibility of a military invasion of Indonesia was considered minuscule, even nearly impossible. The most prominent external threat today was the border dispute in the South China Sea (SCS). Although Indonesia's national interests were disturbed by China's aggressiveness, whose claim over the SCS took a chunk of Indonesia's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) in the North Natuna Sea, Indonesia has always maintained its position as a non-claimant state in the dispute. Nevertheless, regardless of the country's status, current development in the SCS prompted the Indonesian government to prioritize the building of maritime forces around the Natuna Sea.

As an archipelagic state, Indonesia has been relying a lot on its main islands to orchestrate its military organization and operation against ever evolving threats—hence, the main island defense. Nevertheless, it is obvious that the concept of main island defense, that is based on the distribution of territorial commands and is oriented to commit guerrilla warfare of the past, is in need for a conceptual calibration considering the dynamics of strategic environment and ever evolving threats due to rapid development of military technology. It is in this context that a crucial problem arises: how do the existing Indonesian military organization be compatible with the nature of the current threats? This article aims to address the problem by focusing particularly on how the main island defense as the manifestation of Indonesian archipelagic defense may be adaptable to anticipate the new threats. But first, we will discuss the current internal and external threats, both actual and perceived ones, to Indonesia's national security.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2.1 The Main Internal Threats To Indonesia's Main Island Defense

According to Indonesia's latest Defense White Paper (Kementerian Pertahanan RI, 2015), separatism and terrorism remain two major threats to the political integrity of the country. Indonesia has experienced a long history of separatism, especially in the areas that were most recently integrated into the Republic. Throughout the late 1940s to the early 1960s, various rebellions and insurgencies erupted in the regions, such as the rebellion of the Indonesian Communist Party (PKI) and the left-affiliated military faction in 1948 (Susatyo, 2008), the rebellion of the Legion of Ratu Adil (APRA) in 1950, the rebellion of Andi Azis' KNIL (Makassar Uprising) in 1950, the rebellion of PRRI/Permesta in 1958–1960, and the rebellion of Darul Islam/Indonesian Muslim Army (DI/TII) in 1949–1962. Apart from rebellions, several separatist movements also emerged, namely the Republic of South Maluku (Republik Maluku Selatan, RMS) in the Maluku Islands in 1950–1963 (Fatgehipon, 2021), the Free Papua Movement (Organisasi Papua Merdeka, OPM) in Papua from 1967 to the present (Nufus, Mazid, Novitasari, Widiyanto, & Yasnanto, 2019; Anriani, Rahayu, & Salomo, 2021), and the Free Aceh Movement (Gerakan Aceh Merdeka, GAM) in Aceh in 1977–2006 (Ansori, 2012).

The RMS insurgency in Maluku was resolved in 1963 with a military operation which involved a joint operation of the three branches of the Indonesian Armed Forces and mobile troops deployed from other islands (Widjajanto, 2010). At the time, the joint forces under the leadership of Colonel Kawilarang, who previously carried out military operations to quell the Andi Azis rebellion in Makassar, were mobilized to overcome the RMS. Although the RMS

was officially terminated in 1963, until now there have been several incidents of the RMS flag-raising. Therefore, the potential of its re-emergence has been perceived as a threat in today's defense policy (Kementerian Pertahanan RI, 2015).

The GAM insurgency in Aceh was resolved through the Helsinki Agreement in 2006 between the Indonesian government and GAM. The peace agreement was reached by the conflicting parties shortly after an earthquake and tsunami hit Aceh on 26 December 2005, ravaging the west coast of the province, including its capital city, Banda Aceh, and killing nearly 200,000 people. Although resolved by a peace agreement, the Indonesian government had carried out military operations in Aceh in the 1990s during the reign of President Suharto, and in the early 2000s under the administration of President Megawati. During the period, Aceh had the status of a Military Operations Area (Daerah Operasi Militer, DOM) so martial law was enforced in there (Hutagalung, 2004). As a part of the 2006 agreement, Aceh was given a special autonomy completed with a regional parliament and local parties (Ansori, 2012). However, today's defense policy still considers some of the former GAM figures as a potential threat, especially those who were unsuccessful in winning public offices through a legitimate political process.

As in the previous two cases, in dealing with the separatist movement in Papua, the Indonesian government has also tended to rely on the military approach. However, the efforts made so far have not achieved the expected results. The OPM continued to operate and has recently been carrying out more frequent attacks, especially on soldiers and policemen assigned to the region (Nufus, Mazid, Novitasari, Widiyanto, & Yasnanto, 2019). Instead of resolving the violent conflict as intended, the militarization of the Papua question burdens Indonesia with various records of alleged human rights violations. It seems that there has been no significant breakthrough to replace the approach with other more promising measures. Six administrations have passed since President Suharto, but until President Joko Widodo's administration, troop deployment from other islands, particularly from Java, was still going on to carry out security operations in Papua. Armed conflicts were also still common, and usually were intensified shortly before, during, or after certain occasions such as the general election or the OPM's birthday. As a result, the human rights issues become a liability for the Indonesian government in resolving the problem.

Terrorism is another threat given special attention in the Defense White Paper. In the last twenty years or so, Indonesia suffered terrorist attacks almost every year, with only two periods with no attack within a year, i.e. 2006–2008 and 2014–2015. Suicide bombing was the most common method employed by terrorists to deliver their attacks. Terrorism in Indonesia was mostly related to radical Islamic groups or jihadist movements, especially those with international affiliations like Al Qaeda in Afghanistan and later, ISIS (Islamic State of Iraq and Syria) in the Middle East.

During the 1980s to the early 2000s, terrorist groups in Indonesia were mostly rooted in the Darul Islam of the 1950s–1960s (Bruinessen, 2002), at least ideologically, and heavily influenced by the combat experience of some of its central figures in Afghanistan in the late 1980s during the Afghan-Soviet war. It continues to evolve along with its encounters with international Islamist movements, especially ISIS which spread in Iraq in the 2010s.

From early 2000s to now, terrorism in Indonesia seems to transform in terms of its perpetrators, methods, and targets. In the early 2000s, most terrorist attacks were executed by the recruits of Jamaah Islamiyah, a jihadist organization that operated mostly in South East Asia and was affiliated with Al Qaeda. After the death of some of its prominent figures like dr. Azhari and Noordin M. Top, the organization seemed to decline and eventually was replaced by several new cells. The emergence of ISIS and violent conflict in Syria, as well as the politically unstable situation of the Middle East region in general, brought about new groups of jihadists. Several terrorist groups that have emerged recently, although organizationally not within the ISIS structure and did move independently as cells, seem to pledge their allegiance to ISIS.

In terms of methods, terrorist attacks of the early 2000s tended to employ suicide bombings relying on the power of the explosion to create maximum damage. The case of the first Bali Bombing of 2002 was the most prominent example. It was then diversified into several other methods, some of which were equipped with relatively lower explosions aiming for harming a specific target. For instance, the cases of book bomb terror in March 2011 targeted several figures from different backgrounds, usually perceived publicly as critical to Islam and Islamic communities. Besides bombing, in some cases, terrorists of the late 2010s and 2020s also conducted attacks using firearms. In 2018, for instance, a group of terrorists attacked the regional police headquarter in Pekanbaru, Riau province, using katana, while in March 2021 a shooting occurred in the national police headquarter in Jakarta.

In terms of targets, terrorist attacks have also transformed. During the early 2000s, there were many bombings targeting churches in various regions, especially during Christmas celebrations. This seems to be related to the legacy of interreligious conflicts that had occurred in several regions in Indonesia shortly after the Reformation of 1998, particularly conflicts between Muslim and Christian groups. In addition, other targets that were usually aimed by terrorist groups were places that symbolize the West, especially the US and its allies, such as American franchise restaurants, hotel chains, and embassies of several Western countries that are considered hostile to Islam. The targets of terrorist attacks then changed, when recent acts of terrorism tended to target the state apparatus, especially the police. In addition, in the early 2010s, there were also several terror bombs targeting specific individuals who were considered enemies of Islam.

In dealing with the various threats above, in terms of the pattern of operations in handling them, there is one tendency that has been practiced by the Indonesian military and security forces since the 1940s until now. Efforts to resolve problems in various regions through military operations (and later, security operations by the anti-terrorism detachment of the Police) tend to be carried out by deploying troops from the central command in Java or other islands/regions. This tendency unwittingly reduces the doctrine of main island defense because of the contradictions it brings. On the one hand, the essence of main island defense is the use of forces that are centralized on each island independently. It means that each island should be a center for its own defense. But on the other hand, the military and security operations carried out rely heavily on the deployment of troops from outside the island/region.

Several factors can be considered to explain why the above contradictions occur. Each major island has different and limited means and infrastructure for defense. This often means that an island's independence in dealing with the threats it faces cannot be fully exercised. The threat also often erupts in a short period of time so that there is an urgency to resolve them quickly before the threat escalates. Some threats, such as separatism in Aceh and Papua, are long term and protracted. The involvement of troops from the central command or other regions then becomes an option to resolve or at least manage these threats to keep them under control. Considering some of these factors, it ultimately points to the need to build troop strength on each main island to organize regional development in order to maintain the balance of overall operation results.

2.2 The South China Sea Dispute And The Likelihood Of Conventional Threats To Indonesia

The South China Sea (SCS) is one of the most contested regions in the world due to its strategic values, especially for the countries in the region but not limited only to them. Many countries outside the region also have their interests regarding the SCS to some extent. In terms of natural resources, there is a huge amount of natural gas and oil beneath its seabed important for future energy security, as well as an abundant stock of food sources provided by the rich marine lives. The SCS is also one of the most important routes for international trade and navigation, connecting the Pacific and the Indian Oceans, making its importance go beyond its geography. It is not surprising, then, that many countries, both in the region and beyond, are pushing their efforts to secure their interests regarding the SCS and causing bilateral as well as multilateral conflicts in the region.

The Border dispute in the SCS has been going on since at least 1974, and directly involved several countries in the region. Conflict of sovereignty has occurred between China and Vietnam, China and the Philippines, while between China and Malaysia, as well as China and Brunei Darussalam the conflict was more of a conflict over sovereign rights. Indonesia, while maintaining its position as a non-claimant state in the SCS disputes, has taken an active role as a facilitator and mediator in the efforts of dispute resolution since the 1990s. However, China's Nine-Dashed Line claim also intersects with Indonesia's EEZ in the Natuna Sea, so several times it has caused tensions between the two countries due to the activities of Chinese fishing vessels and coast guard there that are perceived as a violation by Indonesia.

The problem of the state borders dispute between the countries in the region has been going on for decades, but the rise of China with its assertion of becoming maritime power in the west Pacific has intensified the tension in recent years. Not only disputed by some Southeast Asian countries like Vietnam, the Philippines and Malaysia, it is also contested by denial acts made by the US and its allies asserting their doctrine of the freedom of navigation. The tension in the SCS has also been increasing partly due to military modernizations made by countries in the region. The economic growth of Southeast Asia, higher than the global average, encouraged countries in the region, including Indonesia, to increase their military spending. Indonesia even spent more to strengthen its military power, especially the Navy, on the North Natuna, an island district adjacent to the SCS.

In recent years China has also built artificial islands and military bases in the SCS. Although some experts doubt the effectiveness of the construction, given its location which is too far from mainland China and prone to natural disasters such as hurricanes, this construction inevitably indicates China's intention to control SCS by conducting area denial. In addition, China has also built two aircraft carriers and was about to build a third. This is in line with China's policy to project its power to the SCS region. This of course provoked the US to further intensify its presence at the SCS. As the latest development, the US together with Australia and the UK signed a security pact called the AUKUS pact in 2021. So far it seems that some dramatic turns have been made by the US to offset China's power in the SCS. First, the US intensified its fleet presence in the SCS by conducting aircraft carrier patrols in the region. Second, the US and its allies also began to station their troops in Australia.

In addition, to contain China, the US seems to still be relying on the first islands chain that confines China, starting from the islands of Japan, Taiwan, down to the Philippines. It should be noted, however, that, unlike Japan and Taiwan, which have taken a tough and hostile stance against China, in recent years the Philippines has been seen to have prioritized a hedging strategy by balancing its stand between China and the US, avoiding an overly biased stance towards either.

Likewise, by sticking to the doctrine of a free and active foreign policy, Indonesia tends to balance its relations with the two conflicting world powers—trying to establish good relations and maintain good rapport with China and the US, without being too biased towards either. It is undeniable that Indonesia's economic cooperation with China has strengthened in recent years. Not only that, diplomatic channels through other fields outside the economy have also strengthened, especially in terms of cultural diplomacy. Since the 2000s, it is even recorded that the military diplomacy between Indonesia and China has also made significant progress, particularly through visiting missions, visits by high-ranking military officers, and even the purchase of military weapons. However, until now the cooperation in the defense sector between Indonesia and the US was still stronger and more developed than that between Indonesia and China, although from time to time Indonesia seems to favour taking steps in diversifying its military weapons by establishing cooperation with more countries, such as China, Russia, South Korea, and Turkey.

At this point, it appears that Indonesia's hedging strategy is still directed at securing its main interest in SCS, namely upholding its sovereignty over the Natuna Sea. Although diplomacy remains Indonesia's primary means of achieving conflict resolution in the SCS, particularly through the ASEAN forum, it is undeniable that in recent years the military approach has also been enforced. As already mentioned, Indonesia has taken steps to strengthen its military and increase its deterrence in the Natuna Islands region, especially against China, despite its closer economic relations with the country.

As seen from the discussion above, Indonesia's position in the SCS conflict, which insists on being a non-claimant state, is a manifestation of its strategy emphasizing diplomacy based on the principle of free and active foreign policy. With this position, the possibility of Indonesia's direct involvement in a possible war in the SCS is small. Likewise, the possibility of a direct

invasion of part of Indonesia's territory as a result of the SCS conflict is also minimal. Nevertheless, should a war break out in the SCS (Mearsheimer, 2014), especially between the US and China, it is likely that Indonesia will have to face conventional forms of threats in the form of spill-over wars or access wars. This is due to Indonesia's geographical proximity to the conflicted area, as well as its strategic position between the SCS and the US military base in Australia.

In securing its interests in the SCS, China's military approach is dominated by an Anti-Access/Area Denial (A2/AD) strategy relying on Long-Range Precision Strike, Ballistic Missile Defense (BMD), Surface and Undersea Operations, Information Operation (IO), Space and Counterspace, Cyber Operations, Integrated Air Defense System (IADS), and Air Operation capabilities (US Office of the Secretary of Defense, 2019, pp. 54-58). On the other hand, the US still relies on militarization of the first island chain aiming to contain China's forces. In this first island chain, there are several US military bases in its major allied countries, especially in South Korea and Japan. In addition, there is also a US Naval Force and Air Force base in Guam, which is part of the second island chain. Recently, the US also tried to strengthen its position in the Indo-Pacific region by initiating the formation of the AUKUS Pact with Australia and the UK in September 2021.

In the context of the SCS dispute, both China and the US have built theatre commands that emphasize the strengthening of weapon systems and multi-domain operations that include land, sea, air, space and cyber domains. The magnitude of the China and the US military build-up in the Indo-Pacific region, supported by the sophistication of their military technology, may allow the forces of the two countries to enter Indonesia's sovereign territory to gain strategic access in order to control the SCS. This development is seriously challenging to the efforts of increasing the relevance of Indonesia's main island defense, which is based on the concept of using main island forces independently for protracted warfare (guerrilla).

2.3 The Military Organization Of Tni And The Nature Of Main Island Defense

Indonesia's defense behavior, especially in dealing with a military threat, cannot be separated from its geographical conditions and the doctrines it holds, particularly those related to war. Considering the geographical condition of a vast archipelago stretching as far as three thousand kilometres, it is reasonable for Indonesia to develop an archipelagic defense system. Main island defense is the backbone of this system. However, this seems to be tautological to signify Indonesia's defense as 'archipelagic' without further adequate explanation on how the main island defense is established as the way to implement it. To better understand this, it is necessary to first examine the war-related doctrine held by the Indonesian military.

Several important points in the Indonesian doctrine of war deserve our emphasis in the context of our discussion. First, Indonesia would not wage a war, unless it was invaded. Accordingly, the Indonesian military was not built for power projection beyond its territory and was not designed to be aggressive. Second, in the event of an invasion by foreign powers, the defense will be focused on the main islands which are expected to be able to secure their territory independently. Third, in defending itself against invasion, the strength and resources of each

main island will be mobilized to carry out a protracted war or war of attrition, so that later momentum can be created to launch an effective counterattack necessary to achieve a decisive victory. Fourth, the war will be carried out as a 'total war,' meaning that all components of the nation are directed to support the achievement of the war's objectives. These points are what construct Indonesia's defense as 'active defensive'.

From the concept of war above, which became known as the Doctrine of Territory War (Doktrin Perang Wilayah), we see that the concept of 'territory' includes at least two layers of conceptual constructs. The first definition covers the entire archipelago, including the territorial waters that stretch in between the islands, as one political unit of the Indonesian nation-state whose integrity must be maintained at all costs. In the second sense of the concept, especially at the tactical and operational level, a territory is a part of Indonesian soil constructed as a 'strategic compartment' where a protracted war can be carried out independently in each compartment. To enable each region to independently engage with their resistance, every main island will serve as the centre of their war logistic system. Consequently, there will be a need to decentralize command and control to ensure the success of each mission (Osinga, 2007).

By the defense concept above, the organization of the Indonesian military is structured with a fairly strong territorial character. This is seen in all the three branches of the Indonesian military, although the most prominent is in the Army. The organization of the Army is hierarchically arranged into commands imitating the administrative division of the civilian government. At the national level, there is an army headquarter, then below it is regional commands (Komando Daerah Militer or Kodam, supervising several Korem, usually in charge of an area equal to that of a province or combination of some provinces), sub-regional commands (Komando Resor Militer or Korem, in charge of several Kodim), district commands (Komando Distrik Militer or Kodim, usually at the city/district level, overseeing several Koramil), sub-district commands (Komando Rayon Militer or Koramil, usually at the sub-district level), and Babinsa (military personnel stationed at the village level). In this complex military organization, regional commands (Kodam) serve as the highest territorial command. Like the Army, Indonesian Police's organization also imitates the levels of civilian government from headquarter at the national level, regional police (Kepolisian Daerah or Polda, usually at the province level), district police (Kepolisian Resor or Polres, usually at the city/district level), sub-district police (Kepolisian Sektor or Polsek, usually at the sub-district level) to Babinkamtibmas (a policeman stationed at the village level). Likewise, the Navy and the Air Force, although not as comprehensive and massive as the Army and the Police, also organized in such a branching hierarchical arrangement, especially to cope with the vastness of Indonesian territory.

At this point, we need to delve deeper into the concept of a strategic compartment in the Indonesian main island defense. In the organization of the Army, under normal conditions, the Kodam acts as a main command of operations. However, should an extraordinary situation emerge, according to the Army's doctrine (2003), the Kodam may function as a strategic compartment, namely a regional command capable of independently carrying out a total defense in its respective region. In such cases, the Kodam also functions as the centre of

command and control to manage their defense area. This function as a strategic compartment is in effect when the country is in a state of military emergency (*darurat militer*) or during the phase of regional resistance (*perlawanan wilayah*) in the event of military invasion by another country.

In terms of archipelagic defense, organizing the military into regional commands spread across all regions in Indonesia is seen as the most effective organization, considering the fragmented shape of the country. However, this territorial organization has also evolved. This evolution is mainly related to the conceptual construct of a ‘strategic compartment’ which sometimes overlays with the area of a main island and sometimes uses completely different territorial delineations. For example, in between 1969–1973 the delineation of a strategic compartment exactly overlaid with the entirety of a large island or a group of islands (island strategic compartment), namely the strategic compartments on the islands of Sumatra, Java and Madura, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Bali and Nusa Tenggara, and also Irian Jaya (Papua) and Maluku. During 1973 to 1985 the concept of ‘composite strategic compartment’ was used. During 1985 to 2019 it was the ‘regional strategic compartment,’ meaning that the delineation of a strategic compartment’s jurisdiction refers to the delineation of a regional command’s (*Kodam*) working area. Then, from 2019 until now, it returns to the composite strategic compartment. It is ‘composite’ in the sense that such a strategic compartment consists of the entirety or a part of a main island, some provinces, and the Archipelagic Sea Line (ASL). Hence, under the latest concept, Indonesia’s territory is organized into three strategic compartments, each under its respective Joint Command of Defense Territory (*Komando Gabungan Wilayah Pertahanan* or *Kogabwilhan*).

The territoriality of the Indonesian Army was deep-rooted in the country’s modern history. The TNI’s territorial command system can be traced back to the period of the independence war of 1945–1949 and the subsequent period of regional insurgencies in 1950s. During the independence war, *wehrkreise* or ‘military regions’ (Said, 1993; Cribb, 2001) was applied to overcome several shortcomings in facing the Dutch ‘police action,’ including poorly consolidated military organization, lack of experience and educated military personnel, lack of weapons and ammunitions, as well as lack of communication infrastructure to organise scattered forces in separated islands. In the aftermath of dealing with regional insurgencies, territorial commands resulting from the evolution of the *wehrkreise* system as well as several internal security stabilization acts were perceived as a necessity to anticipate and prevent future insurgencies.

Within the course of Indonesian modern history, the internal/domestic and external threats have been constantly threatening Indonesia’s national security, although their manifestations and intensity vary depending on the dynamics that occur in each period. In the past, in facing the threat of Dutch military aggression, the *wehrkreise* system was effective in defending the country’s newly independence from a stronger invader, the Dutch. When facing separatists and insurgencies, however, the Indonesian military has dealt with weaker opponents and began to build a mobile joint force to carry out ‘counter-insurgencies’ operations. After these rebellions were suppressed—nearly all of them were successfully eradicated or paralyzed by the early

1960s—the legacy of the wehrkreise system still informed the formulation of Indonesia's defense. To anticipate the re-emergence of rebellions and insurgencies in Indonesia's soil throughout the archipelago, the TNI then established territorial commands that were permanently stationed in the regions. Likewise, during the New Order period (1967–1998), the territorial commands became the backbone in detecting and anticipating the potential emergence of terrorism and 'subversive' movements. Intelligence operations became crucial for the effectiveness of this territoriality.

Since the 1998 Reformation and the demands for military reform that followed, the discourse of reviewing or even abolishing territorial commands has surfaced and has never really disappeared nor has been answered completely. The impetus for the review was rooted in the politicization of the military during the New Order era, as one of the main instruments of the state's repressive behavior in maintaining national stability as a prerequisite for the developmentalist agenda. In addition, some also suggest that the abolition of the territorial commands is necessary to increase the efficiency of the Indonesian military budget and to support the realization of civilian supremacy in the political realm. However, the fact is that the territorial command system is still intact today.

Now the question is: how is the Indonesian archipelagic defense system, which is based on the main island defense, compatible with facing the current threats? In this last section, this article will address the problem by focusing on Indonesia's defense behavior against the main threats described in the previous sections. We have seen that in carrying out its defense strategy, Indonesia organizes its territory into smaller sub-territories which are expected to be able to independently carry out resistance in the event of invasion. In this case, the existence of a territorial command is crucial.

This territoriality also seems quite appropriate to deal with the threat of separatism, considering that separatism always occurs locally in a certain region. The aim of the separatist movement is not to overthrow the legitimate central government, but to form its sovereign state by separating itself from the political unity of Indonesia. Thus, counter-insurgency efforts that are focused on an isolated area are reasonable to contain separatist operations. Mobile joint forces can be deployed from outside the region if the conflict escalates to become an open violent conflict.

In dealing with the threat of terrorism, a slightly different strategy seems necessary because the characteristics of the threat are also different from separatism. The main purpose of terrorism is to undermine the state, overthrow the legitimate government, or even replace the state ideology with the ideology they are fighting for. The threat of terrorism does not have clear territorial boundaries and the movement of the actors is much more dynamic. In this case, inter-regional communication becomes a more crucial instrument in detecting, preventing, and overcoming terrorism.

Nevertheless, in the history of Indonesia, the suppression of regional rebellions has never been carried out only by the territorial unit based in that area but has been carried out by deploying combat units from other islands, especially Java (Prabowo, 2012). Therefore, apart from

territorial units, the TNI also developed combat units organized into brigades, battalions, companies, and squads. The combat units are stationed in several regions, but the largest concentration is on the island of Java. This unit, different from the territorial unit, is mobile. This centralization of combat power in Java has implications for the concentration of the latest defense equipment in Java as well.

The territorial characteristics of the TNI have so far been considered quite effective because they are based on three basic assumptions. The first assumption is that the invasion of Indonesia, given its archipelagic geography, was inevitably aimed at ‘centres of gravity’ in some regions, as happened in the two Dutch Aggressions in 1947–1948 (Said, 1993). Therefore, the organization of military regions (wehrkreise) seems to be the most appropriate decision to enable the utilization of forces effectively and efficiently, given the limitations of power to covering Indonesia’s vast, separated land area.

Future invasions will likely have two purposes: to occupy a region and/or enforce a regime change. The most recent example of invasions aiming for an occupation is the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 aimed at occupying the Donbas region consisting of Donetsk and Luhansk in Eastern Ukraine. Even with Russia’s declaration of its recognition of the sovereignty of Donetsk and Luhansk, the chance is that both the region will join the Russian Federation, as was Crimea in 2014. Examples of invasions aiming for a regime change are the US invasions of Afghanistan in 2001 and of Iraq in 2003. The chance of foreign invasions of Indonesia is very small, even almost impossible, because currently there is no country interested in achieving these two political goals by invading Indonesia. In addition, the current world order is no longer the same as in the colonial era, so the occurrence of colonialism is very unlikely.

The second assumption is that TNI’s experiences in carrying out its duties in dealing with threats to Indonesia’s territorial and political integrity were dominated by military operations of counter-insurgencies, as happened from the late 1940s to the early 1960s. These military operations were carried out by containing the rebels within a localized theatre of operation, and then mobilizing mobile combat units to destroy them. For example, the Indonesian military operation to overcome the DI/TII rebellion in West Java in the 1960s (Operasi Pagar Betis) (Soebardi, 1983).

Threats (and their handling) that are localized, as happened during the period of parliamentary democracy and guided democracy above, have now undergone changes, especially with the evolution of threats so that they are more dominated by terrorism. Separatism that occurred locally in a region, currently only takes place in Papua. GAM separatism in Aceh can be considered to have disappeared after the signing of the Helsinki Agreement in 2006 (Ansori, 2012). The presence of armed groups in Poso, Central Sulawesi, led by Santoso (East Indonesian Mujahidin or Mujahidin Indonesia Timur/MIT), shows the mixed characteristics of terrorism and separatism. This armed group was also neutralized through a military operation in 2011.

Terrorism that occurred in Indonesia during the early 2000s and 2010s was partly rooted in the DI/TII ideology. This shows how separatism (aimed at separating themselves from Indonesia

and establishing their sovereign state) of the 1950s-1960s had evolved into terrorism (aimed at overthrowing the legitimate government and/or changing the state ideology). However, since the emergence of ISIS in the Middle East, terrorism in Indonesia has been more influenced by internationalist ideology, especially the caliphate. The threat of terrorism, unlike the separatist movement, doesn't recognize locality, so it cannot be handled through territorial independence. Rather, the prioritization of coordination and exchange of intelligence information between regions is a must.

The third assumption, in the event of an invasion, the war scenario still follows the conventional pattern, where the enemy's attack will take place linearly from the outside to the inside, starting from the outer theatre (mandala luar), to the inner theatre (mandala dalam), to the struggle base area (daerah pokok perlawanan). In the outer theatre, war will occur at sea so the Navy and the Air Force will play a dominant role. In the inner theatre, the enemy will carry out the process of landing troops so that there will be a coastal battle. In the next phase, if the hostile forces cannot be stopped or destroyed during the sea or coastal battle, the resistance will be carried out through guerrilla warfare within the resistance base area. In this last stage, the main islands will become the basis of resistance and are expected to be able to fight independently using all of their resources. Thus, a total war will be orchestrated in the arena of each main island.

The war scenario above seems to be outdated or at least deserves to be rethought. Modern warfare, especially that seen in the US invasions of Afghanistan in 2001 and of Iraq in 2003, as well as Russia invasion of Ukraine in 2022, is no longer linear from the outside in. With the advent of the latest war technologies, the first attack can be carried out directly in the enemy's backyard. The existence of long-range cruise missiles, and even Intercontinental Ballistic Missiles (ICBM), as well as unmanned aircraft (drones) capable of reconnaissance and attack at the same time, allow war to be carried out not in a linear fashion. Moreover, it is not invasion that threatens Indonesia's sovereign territory in the future, as discussed in the previous section, but the possibility of spill-over war or access war resulting from armed conflict in the SCS.

Based on the considerations above, the territorial characteristics of the Indonesian military and the main island defense system need to be adjusted or modified to be able of responding to current challenges and threats. The development of main island defense needs to be implemented in an integrated military strategy. The urgency of single command control on each main island is a necessity to achieve this goal. In this case, the development of main island defense that can transcend the contextuality of protracted war or guerrilla warfare of the past is a strategic answer in facing future threats that evolve along with the rapid development of weapons technology. There are at least four defense patterns that can be developed to make the main island defense relevant. First, is the so-called inner-island defense, i.e. the defense of the resistance base area, concentrating on the hinterland where protracted war is conducted using guerrilla warfare. In this context, the function of the Kodam as a strategic compartment seems to remain relevant.

Second, is the so-called intra-island defense, by which the resistance within an island is carried out through the coordination between Kodams there. In the past, there were inter-regional commands (Komando Antar Daerah/Koanda) whose role was to coordinate the adjacent

Kodams, and then the defense territory commands (Komando Wilayah Pertahanan/Kowilhan) based on each main island. Today, such an organization no longer exists. Kodam is now the highest territorial unit with an area of operation covering one or a few provinces. Intra-island defense also needs to be supported by appropriate technology. To make it effective, weapon systems with a firing range of 500-1,000 km need to be stationed on each island, such as field artillery missiles and air defense artillery. For each island, it is also necessary to establish a single command to organize all defense forces across the island.

Third, is the so-called inter-island defense. By this scheme, territorial units from different islands are expected to be able to support one another when needed to do so. Currently, Indonesia has a type of organization called the Joint Command of Defense Territory (Kogabwilhan). It is expected to facilitate the implementation of inter-island defense. However, Kogabwilhan's task is only coordinating in nature. It would be extremely hard to rely on it for mobilizing territorial units from different islands into one effective armed force. As with intra-island defense, inter-island defense also needs to be supported with weapon systems whose firing range is up to 1,000 km. With such weapon systems, it will be more possible for each island to protect each other.

Fourth, is the so-called cross-domain defense. The conventional wisdom of warfare puts reliance on the strength of ground troops, while the sea and the air forces' main task is to provide support and assistance, for example by a bombardment before the infantry enters the targeted area. In a cross-domain defense, the opposite method of fighting needs to be developed, where land units must be able to provide support and assistance to sea and air forces in the battle area. Take, for example, regarding the possible armed conflict in the SCS, should the Indonesian Navy and Air Force confront the Chinese naval fleet, the land defense forces near the area should assist. By utilizing cruise missiles capable of reaching a distance of hundreds to 1,000 km, artillery units located in West Kalimantan and the east coast of Sumatra can provide support for the Navy and the Air Force in the SCS area. Advances in rocket technology used in these cruise missiles will be able to compensate for the absence of aircraft carriers which are currently the mainstay of maritime powers such as the US and have also been developed by China to improve its superiority in the SCS.

3. CONCLUSION

At first glance, the main island defense may seem irrelevant to Indonesia, for several reasons. Firstly, on the one hand, the likelihood of an invasion of Indonesia today and in the near future is nearly impossible, while on the other hand, the techniques of warfare have undergone significant changes and are far different from those of the Second World War. Therefore, it is an anachronism to apply the doctrine of territorial warfare that was formulated more than half a century ago. Second, separatism and terrorism have never been handled by relying solely on the regional forces, but have always been supported by the deployment of combat units from the central or other regions. Third, one of the main threats today is the dynamics in the SCS, situated outside Indonesian territory. One of the problems that should be considered is if there is an open violent conflict between China and the US and its allies in the South Pacific,

especially Australia, how will Indonesia position itself with its archipelagic defense concept? To answer the issues, as discussed in this article, it is very important to update the main island defense system with schematics consisting of inner-island, intra-island, inter-island, and cross-domain defense, as offered by the authors. To make this scheme effective, it is also necessary to reform the organization of the Indonesian military including military operations driven by using its applicable technology.

4. REFERENCES

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